

Scripture or Tradition
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Mark 7:1-13

¹ The Pharisees and some of the scribes gathered around Him when they had come from Jerusalem, ² and had seen that some of His disciples were eating their bread with pure hands, that is, unwashed. ³ (For the Pharisees and all the Jews do not eat unless they carefully wash their hands, *thus* observing the traditions of the elders; ⁴ and *when they come* from the market place, they do not eat unless they cleanse themselves; and there are many other things which they have received in order to observe, such as the washing of cups and pitchers and copper pots.) ⁵ The Pharisees and the scribes asked Him, "Why do Your disciples not walk according to the tradition of the elders, but eat their bread with impure hands?" ⁶ And He said to them, "Rightly did Isaiah prophesy of you hypocrites, as it is written: 'THIS PEOPLE HONORS ME WITH THEIR LIPS, BUT THEIR HEART IS FAR AWAY FROM ME. ⁷ 'BUT IN VAIN DO THEY WORSHIP ME, TEACHING AS DOCTRINES THE PRECEPTS OF MEN.' ⁸ "Neglecting the commandment of God, you hold to the tradition of men." ⁹ He was also saying to them, "You are experts at setting aside the commandment of God in order to keep your tradition. ¹⁰ "For Moses said, 'HONOR YOUR FATHER AND YOUR MOTHER'; and, 'HE WHO SPEAKS EVIL OF FATHER OR MOTHER, IS TO BE PUT TO DEATH'; ¹¹ but you say, 'If a man says to *his* father or *his* mother, whatever I have that would help you is Corban (that is to say, given *to God*),' ¹² you no longer permit him to do anything for *his* father or *his* mother; ¹³ *thus* invalidating the word of God by your tradition which you have handed down; and you do many things such as that."

For 2000 years, the church has been creating ordinances for the people of God to follow. Many of these ordinances are not based on biblical Scripture but on the theological beliefs developed over the centuries. For example, in the Catholic Church, a priest cannot be married. This ordinance came from feudalism when the inheritance was given to the firstborn male of the family. When priests had children, the church building and its property could be passed down to the firstborn child; thus, the church would lose income. To stop this income loss, an ordinance was created that prevents priests from marrying. Today it is called a tradition of the church. Illegitimate children could not inherit property during feudalism. There is no commandment in the Scripture that says that the servants of God cannot be married. This is just one example of many places where the church has created ordinances to control people and sometimes obscure the Scripture's true meaning.

Martin Luther, in 1517 CE, started what is called the Reformation. He was not the first reformer but rather the first reformer who was not killed by the church. Luther's first problem with the church was over the paying of indulgences for the forgiveness of sin. When Luther started to translate the New Testament into German, he discovered many

ordinances that the church had created that were not biblical. Besides, the Catholic Church stated that tradition trumped the Bible. The Protestant churches that arose from Luther's Reformation changed based on Luther's belief that the Bible must be first. Today, several Protestant churches will say that the Bible comes first but put their ordinance books and regulations ahead of the Scripture. When a Protestant denomination places its ordinance book before the Bible, then that denomination is no longer Protestant.

Traditions are important and should not be discarded quickly. However, traditions of the church that are in direct conflict with the Scripture must be removed. Traditions that are not biblically based should have their foundation examined as to the motive for creating the tradition. In Jesus' day, the Temple leaders were using their developed traditions and regulations to control the people's lives. Jesus said that this is wrong. The LORD's Law is all that the people need to live a life that pleases the LORD.

If the church is based on the words and teachings of Jesus, it is not in compliance with this Scripture passage. Jesus was clearly against the church creating traditions and regulations that controlled lives that were not biblically based. The church people have to start asking the question, Why are church leaders doing what Jesus condemned? That is a profound statement to make and will upset the church leaders. Organizations create hierarchy, and the people in the leadership positions like being there. They are not going to give up the power they have accumulated over the centuries through traditions and regulations that are not biblically based. The last time the people revolted was in 1517. It is time for a NEW REFORMATION!

May the LORD bless you in your learning and studying of His Word.